

Values-Based Education in the Digital World: Exploring the Influence of Social Values on Individual Experiences in Cyberspace and Their Convergence with Pashtun Cultural Values

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Abstract: *Does cyber culture have any value-based system? The question is indeed intriguing because it touches the fundamentals of the overarching cyber sphere. The present study investigates the experiences of people within the cyber sphere and the ways in which values are practiced in the cyber world. This study also examines the interaction between Pashtun cultural values and digital values to understand the pinnacle point of the confluence of Pashtun cultural values and digital values. The primary concern of the present study is to identify the parallels between Pashtun social values and digital values. The study employs a hybrid model methodological framework which includes the persona and a diagnostic map, as an interrogative tool to identify experiences of users in cyberspace. In addition, the researcher also employs an affinity diagramming as a research method to categorize the various values collected from interviews, articles, and Pashtun stories. The findings of the study reveal the existence of an unwritten code of ethics in the cyberspace that is constituted on our socio-cultural values. The study develops parallels between Pashtun code of nang, gherat, mashari and pardah with the digital values of privacy, mentorship, security, trustworthiness and service enabling, respectively. These initiatives aim to create a more suitable environment for people to participate in protecting their privacy.*

Keywords: Cyberspace, Pashtun Values, Digital Values, Nang, Purdah, Privacy, Service Enabling

Introduction

Azarakhs Ziaie, Mehdi, Shaniz Anjani and Amir Manian (2021) in their research identify 9 (Nine) sets of Digital values. These values includes vividness, mobility, peer communication, personalization, interactivity, connectivity, Values co-creation, telepresence and information availability (pg.1). In addition to this, Araz Zirar (2023), in his research also highlights several digital values like precision, efficiency, capability, speed, flexibility, guidance, and emotional support (Pg. 2,8,9). These instances of digital values direct us to question the source of these

values. UWEV. Riss, Michael Ziegler, and Lindsay J. Smith (2022), maintain that digital value actually comes from the social system. Digital values are created through a systematic process that corresponds to the individual demands and needs in a social environment (Pg.1). This further leads to an integral question as to whether there exists any link between digital values and social value that we have in our society.? BELGHIT Muhammad Tayeb (2024) in his article argues that some of the social value like “solidary, equality, and respect” can also be found in the digital system which shows that there is a link between digital and social worlds. Social values are not something idiosyncratic to an individual, rather, they are embedded in the customs of each culture.

Pashtun culture, practiced in Pakistan and Afghanistan, has been present since ages. It is a rich culture with diverse customs and practices in both countries. However, there is a common thread that bind all the regional differences of the Pashtun culture into one unified whole. This fine thread is Pashtunwali. The code of life of Pashtuns of Pakistan and Afghanistan. TILAK DESASHER (2023), in his research identifies Pashtun values such as “Ghairat / Nang”, Badal, Melmastya, Purdah, Namus, Gender Difference, and Shura, (Pg. 17) Fundamental to the Pashtunwali code. Similarly, Fasih Ur Rehman, Sana Saeed, and Maham Nawaz (2024) in their research identified numerous Pashtun Value including honesty bravery, respect for the elder, *Hujra, Gudar, Jirga, Purdah, Nang, Namus, Ghairat, Melmastya, Nanawatye, Badal, Equality, Tura, Musawat* and *Merana* that constitute the lives of Pashtuns (Pg.69). The identification of these values leads us to fundamental questions related to the experiences of individuals in digital world.

Research Objectives

1. To explore the influence of social values on an individual’s experience in cyberspace.
2. To examine the parallels between Pashtun social values and digital values.

Research Questions:

1. How do social values constitute an individual’s experience in the digital world?
2. To what extent Pashtun social values align with digital values?

Context & Partnership:

This project was conducted by researchers from Khushal Khan Khattak University Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, in partnership with two local school i.e. Karak Model School Karak and Sir Syed Model School Karak. The present research project was funded by activities the research team and involve academia’s who are part of IPIR which is a global network of postgraduate student and new researcher. This study focuses ICTD (Information and Communication Technology for Development) where the researcher means to use technology to digitize past proverb.

Literature Reviews

Araz Zirar (2023) in his research argues that technological advancement of worksites has launched an innovative digital agent called a digital human, which can communicate and operate like actual human beings. The researcher explores the potential benefits and shortcomings of digital humans in creating value. The researcher aimed to find the distinctive function the digital human can perform in boosting workspace productivity, security, and human expertise. The researcher also examines that how society, technology, and law can limit their complete incorporation. The primary objective of the researcher was to highlight the value that digital humans can provide to the workplace and organization. The researcher employs a manual, database, specific search, and systematic search approach for the detailed review of 62 articles. The researcher uses thematic analysis as a research methodology to uncover the important points and themes of the selected article. Zirar (2023) argues that digital humans are used in workspaces to alleviate the exhaustion and distress of the worker and also to prevent design mistakes. The researcher also claims that digital humans can help in labor shortages, with minimal cost, providing emotional help, and provide knowledge and direction (Zirar, 2023).

Anwar Mohyuddin and Nasra Khan (2023) in their research maintains that Pashtun values are vastly declining its importance due to its male-dominated system. The researchers aim to find the reason behind the loss of conventional Pashtun values in Pashtun society. They also examine the social, political, and economic factors that led to the decline of such value. Furthermore, the researcher examined the impact that value deterioration has not only on the Pashtun people but on the country as a whole. The researchers employ cultural relativism, social change theory, and the Frankfurt school model of socio-cultural theory to analyze values that are socially constructed and also to examine the impact of factors like media, education, and wealth on the shaping of these values. The researcher adopted a qualitative anthropological approach as a research methodology to collect the data from in-depth interviews, participant observation, Case studies, and purposive sampling. The researcher gathered data from two sources. The primary source is the Interview conducted in village Chakdara and case study, while the secondary sources are books, articles, and media. Mohyuddin & Khan, (2023) argue that media play a crucial role in fostering a Western lifestyle, which replaced the traditional values of Pashtun society. The researchers further maintains that globalization is a major factor that contributes to the demolishing of family unity and thus leads toward the loss of cultural identity and ethical values. Additionally, the researcher argues that wealth creates division among people in society, thus eliminating the sense of helping people, and with this migration, it also outcome in the loss of cultural norms. The researcher concluded that their Pashtun values, like Nang, Namus, Izzat, Ghairat, Masher/ Kashir, jirga, melmastya, etc., are confronting severe warnings from both the internal and external factors. However, with the help of education, Policy, communal engagement, and awareness, we can protect and revive Pashtun cultural values (Mohyuddin & khan, 2023).

Mohammad Tayeb, in his article explores the changes of social values with the advancement and evolution of technology. The study aims to investigate the impacts of digitization on the core social values, such as the choices of the individual, behaviors, and interpersonal relationships. The study also examines the different aspects of digital

technologies that influence social values. The researcher attempts to answer how our social values are shaped by digital technology and how it influences our interpersonal relations and interactions in daily life. The study uses a multidisciplinary approach from various fields, such as social sciences, psychology, communication, and technological studies, as a methodological framework to inspect the intersection between Social Values and digital technology. The researcher collected data from different research articles, books, reports, and academic publications on social values. The researchers also conducted an online survey in terms of Questionnaires from 100 Facebook users between the ages of 18 and 65 regarding social values such as privacy, respect, and their relations. The researcher argues that digital technology has brought significant changes in the interpersonal relationship. The social apps have changed the way of communication of the people. This relationship based on the digital is fragmented, and people are emotionally detached from each other. The researcher further argues that with the evolution of digital technology, the misuse and identity of people are more at risk. In addition, the study explains that with the digital technology, individuals have access to a lot of information. The researcher concludes from the analysis that the digital age has given opportunities and also concerns and challenges for maintaining the social values. Further, the study explored that a lot of changes occur in the relationship of people with each other with the advancement of technology, and people have also been given access to each and everything.

Methodology

The present study adopted a hybrid model as a methodological framework for the research project. This model is suitable for this research because it allows students from different levels (school to university level) and different areas to work together for understanding different Pashtun and digital values, contemporary world, and also to learn from each other's experiences.

This study includes a planning session or strategy meeting, a reflection session or evaluation discussion, and a co-located session. A Planning session or strategy meeting was carried out at the start of every phase to talk about the arrangement and set strategies for the activities that are going to be held. Secondly, a reflection session or evaluation discussion was carried out at the final stage of every phase to analyze the performed exercises or activities and make strategies for the upcoming process. Thirdly, a co-located session was conducted multiple times at the university and a local school in a co-located setting with physical presence. This hybrid model is considered more efficient than the conventional face-to-face approach, but this model retains the communication aspects of the ancient face-to-face approach. This hybrid model combines a classical face-to-face approach with self-reflection time, which is very beneficial for the student because it gives them plenty of time to reflect on their own thoughts and ideas about the given topic. In contrast to conventional face to face communication where students from same area, same grade and same age can interact with each other while on the other hand this hybrid model enable the students from different areas, grades, and age group to interact and learn from each other about various cultures, Digital Values, and their importance in today's world.

The members of the local management group, including researchers, school teachers, and undergraduate students, develop a plan for the session and design a strategy to achieve fruitful results from the activities. Each researcher selects a specific topic related to digital experience, examining the impacts that it creates and exploring the relationship between Digital and Pashtun Values to overcome a certain issue.

In the course of all these sessions and activities, the research team member noticed how these Junior School students, postgraduate students, and elderly people participated, interacted, and took part in the activities, particularly in sharing their thoughts about their digital experience, Pashtun Values, and Digital Values. The researchers carried out an extensive study and investigation of the stories behind Pashto proverbs, concentrating on the viewpoints of young learners, graduate students, and older adults. The researchers analyzed the degree of understanding and passion among these groups regarding different Values, especially focusing on the Pashtun culture's Values like Pashtunwali, Melmastya, Ghairat, Honor, Nang, respect for elders, and the stories behind Pashto proverbs. These tasks encouraged the participants to freely share their ideas about the fundamental values of their own culture.

The researcher undertook a focus group discussion at Khushal Khan Khattak University, Karak, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. This discussion was joined by six student members, all of whom are currently enrolled in MPhil studies. The student's age varies from 25 to 32 years. All the participants were students of literature, and they also came from different ethnic backgrounds and villages within District Karak, including Chokara, Warana, Ghulam Khel, Takht-e-Nasrati, Jahangiri, and Ahmadabad.

To fulfill the aim of our research objectives, the researcher employed specialized tools for a better understanding of users, including the Persona model and a five-element relationship diagnostic map. The main reason behind using a persona model is that the participant felt comfortable in sharing their feelings and information about a particular topic. They were asked to develop a fictional character for themselves so that they feel comfortable sharing their experiences without fear of being judged. After developing their persona, the participants were asked to use a human relationship diagnostic tool to talk about the problems, issues, and challenges their character experienced while developing a sincere relationship in the digital world. This method helped the participant to know about their digital experiences, its causes, problems, impacts, and what kind of solutions are required to tackle ethical issues in the digital world. During the discussion, the researcher prepared a script of the conversation, which was later used for the thematic analysis.

Along with focus group activity, the researchers also undertook interviews with 32 participants from different localities and diverse age groups, ranging from 40 to 85 years. This group consists of both male and female interviewees. Each of the participants was asked eight to 10 specific questions, which were set by the researcher, to collect their thoughts and perspective about Pashtun cultural values. They were also asked to share any Pashto proverbs, stories, or quotes related to Pashtun cultural values.

Results

1. Initial Observation and Discussion:

As already discussed in the above section that each research member observed and had a discussion with students and elderly people from different areas, ages, and gender to record their attention and perspectives about social, cultural, traditional, and digital values, and whether these values have changed with the passage of time or transform into another form in the digital world. The results from all the participants are surprisingly coherent and exhibit a steady shift of values through passage of time. However, each participant also faces their own issue related to their performance in the digital space. Lack of cyber ethics has been recognized as a major problem in Pakistan, which reached its peak because of the excessive use of the internet and mobile phones. People are subjected to online harassment through different networking sites, texting apps, and other social platforms. The situation becomes more serious in Pakistan due to a lack of value-based education, digital training, and parental contribution. Thus, people lose trust in cyberspace due to the prevalence of everyday scams.

2. Persona:

The researcher adopted the persona method at the first stage of the focus group discussion. The participants develop their own persona. The researcher has a total of six (6) persons from different areas. The basic purpose of persona creation was to achieve truthful and natural responses from the participants. As a result of persona development, the participants felt a sense of dissociation; they felt like they were stepping outside of themselves while sharing their thoughts, problems, and hopes. **Table. 1**

Persona No.1	Persona No.2	Persona No.3
<p>Name: Aneela Age: 25 years Old Belongs to: Chokara Family Background: Father: Teacher, Authoritative. Mother: Nurse, Busy Loves: Animation Cartoons Siblings: Youngest of three brothers. Favorite color: Pink Hobby: Making Reels Love: A boy who leaked her chat Frustration: Disappointment Wants: Privacy</p>	<p>Name: Kalsoom Age: 27 Years Old Belongs to: Warana Family Background: Strict family background Sibling: Second among three brothers. Favorite Color: Red Hobby: Reading romantic novel secretly. Love: Chatting a boy out of curiosity who later exposed her. Frustration: Nervousness, Fear of shame. Wants: Honorable and respectable life.</p>	<p>Name: Saira Begum Age: 32 Years Old Belongs to: Ghulam Khel, Karak Family Background: Father is Shopkeeper, Mother is Teacher. Sibling: Third among six siblings (Three brothers and three sisters) Favorite Color: Red, Blue and Green. Hobby: Making dress design and rarely upload it on Instagram. Love: To learn Unique design. Frustration: Lack of parental care, mock of unsocial. Love: Introvert, not having relation with anyone. Wants: Parental love.</p>

Persona No.4	Persona No. 5	Persona No. 6
<p>Name: Munazza Jabeen Age: 28 years old Belongs to: Takht e Nasrati, Karak Family Background: Father died, Mother health worker. Sibling: Two elder brother and one younger sister. Favorite Color: Green Hobby: Nature photography, Cooking Love: Never in relation but once take selfie with classmates, which one of them use for fake profile. Frustration: Mental stress, Depression Wants: To become a Web developer or Chief.</p>	<p>Name: Murtaza Rehman Age: 32 Years Old Belongs to: Ahmadabad, Karak Family Background: Father is Laborer, Mother is housewife. Sibling: Only Child Favorite Color: Grey Hobby: Drawing, Painting, and upload it unanimously. Love: Online relation with girl who called herself an art teacher but stolen his painting. Frustration: Feel isolated, Painting loss. Wants: To become an artist, Loyal friends.</p>	<p>Name: Muhammad Azlan Age: 30 Years Old. Belongs to: Jahangiri Banda, Karak Family Background: Father is Engineer but strict and conservative, Mother is housewife. Sibling: Eldest out of six sisters Favorite Color: Blue Hobby: Writing prose and poetry about women problem. Love: Once share a poem in friends group about cycle but they share everywhere and make fun of him. Frustration: Menta Stress. Wants: To become an activist.</p>

Diagnostic Map

The researcher uses a diagnostic map, which is a tool that helps to identify problems, understand their causes and effects, and see how they are connected to each other. A diagnostic map breaks down a problem into its key parts, including important factors and elements that are relevant to the situation being studied. For this purpose, we requested the participants to shed light on the five aspects of their online experiences.

1.1. Hope:

Despite all the problems and threats, the developing persona of both boys and girls has some hope, which includes having their own privacy, living an honorable life, and receiving their parents' attention. Some of them want to become app developers, artists, and activists so that they can serve their community.

1.2. Problems:

The common problems that different persona dealt with were the loss of personal information, pictures, and videos by some unknown people on the digital media, which leads to the erosion of their honor and dignity. Some of them also face the problems of being insulted and ridiculed publicly. One of the persona has lost his artwork, which was stolen by a unanimous girl. Additionally, they also confront restrictive parental rules, which often cause mental stress and anxiety.

1.3. Impacts:

The impacts of these problems lead to increased disappointment, augmented nervousness, fear of being looked down upon, loneliness, mental stress, and isolation. In short, their digital experiences have left severe effect on the aforementioned personas that sometimes have triggered suicidal attempts in the personas, and thus abuse and shame.

1.4. Causes:

All these problems occur due to the misuse and absence of a digital ethical code. Young generation spends plenty of time on social media, which exposes them and to digital harassment and similar issues. Secondly, there is a lack of educational content that teaches basic manners and polite behavior. Important values like kindness, respect for privacy, help, and courtesy are no longer taught in schools and books. Additionally, the busy and strict nature of parents also has a role in such cases. Parents want their children to be pure and honorable, without giving time to teach them the important values and make them conscious about the use of digital resources.

1.5. Solution:

A possible solution to resolve these issues is to promote value-based education through digital resources such as websites, eBooks, tutorial, and videos. The elder should develop a strong connection with their children and motivate children to learn from digital resources. The children who spend more time on internet will be able to learn their cultural values from these resources. The content for such resources can be used from particular cultural Oral literature, such as proverbs, poems and folk stories.

Discussion:

The research outcomes drawn from the focus group discussion, persona analysis, interviews, and visual diagnostic tools revealed the problems and difficulties that young people are facing in today's digital world. The research identifies that digital world is extremely vulnerable. With the passage of time, new technological innovations (Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram) were introduced, and people are spending more time on these social sites, due to which they are ignoring their traditional, cultural and familial values. Different interviewees have made the statement that in the past, people used to spend time with one another. They would gather in a Hujra, where they would have long talks about different values, such as kindness, hospitality, honor, and respecting elders. Moreover, they point out that in the past, families were supportive, provided children a sense of protection, while the families of today are fragmented, parents are busy, and have no time to teach them the safe use of social media. With the help of the created persona, the researcher also revealed the hope, desire, and goals of the participant, such as wanting to become an artist, activist, and have an honorable digital life to live. Furthermore, they also need parental care to be supported and protected in the cyber world. Overall, the researcher stated that the participant needs value-based education, which should be promoted through both digital media and physical learning institutions as well.

Despite this, the diagnostic analysis exposed some major threats and problems associated with cyberbullying. The first major problem is the misuse of social media platforms, which may bring shame and disgrace to someone's life. Secondly, strict and poor parental connection. It means that parents are busy and do not have time to prepare their children in accordance with the demands of the digital world. Thirdly, the lack of availability of textbooks that convey value-based education. These problems left a severe mark on the mental health of the participants, but they are still resilient and hopeful to overcome the threat and achieve their goal provided that they are equipped with ethics and values to be used in the digital world.

Chapter 3

Affinity Diagram

Furthermore, the researcher also uses an affinity diagramming approach for the collection and categorization of data. Affinity Diagramming is a method that emerged from Japan, initially proposed by Brassard in 1989. The affinity model is quoted by Simson and Friberg, who cite Beyer and Holtzblatt as being broadly employed in various design methods, such as contextual design and participatory design (J. Simson & K. Friberg, 101). Affinity diagramming helps the researcher to collect a large quantity of data. (Simson & Friberg, 101). The present study utilizes the Affinity Diagramming model for the collection and categorization of data. The process was done in four steps.

Step 1:

For this purpose, the researcher conducted interviews with different people, surveying different research articles to gain insight into the various digital values and Pashtun cultural values. The first interviewee began by highlighting the importance of 'Pashtunwali,' which requires Pashtuns to follow the values conveyed by this ancient code of conduct. The second interviewee shed light on 'hospitality (Melmastya), serving and generosity'. The third one talks about "Purdah, Ghairat, Honor". The fourth one point out the importance of "Badal". Revenge / Return. Similarly, many other interviewees discussed Pashtun values, including honor (Nang), respect for elders, the Jirga, Justice, equality, and brotherhood.

According to Araz Zirar (2023), predictability, capability, and speed are some important digital values. Leif Sunderberg (2019) also explores values like durability, accountability, and service enabling in the digital world. According to Dr. Fasih Ur Rehman, Sana Saeed, and Maham Nawaz (2024), Honor, Purdah, Nang, Namus, Melmastya, badal, sharam, Musawat, and respect for elders are important values in Pashtun culture. By comparing values, the researcher found some similarities between both the digital and Pashtun Values.

Step. 2

After collecting the above data from various interviews, surveys, and articles, the researcher wrote all the Values related to the Pashtun and digital systems on colorful sticky notes.

Step 3

After writing values on sticky notes, the researcher creates different categories of Values and places those notes one by one in corresponding columns under the same categories.

Step. 4

Step four is the development of parallels between Pashtun cultural values and digital values. The analysis of interviews and literature related to digital values reveal that some of the Pashtun values, such as Pashtunwali, Hospitality, Purdah, Ghairat / Honor, Elder Respect, and Mentorship, have a close resemblance with the digital values of privacy, service enabling, mentoring, and protection against cyber attack. Similarly, the same Values are also present in Pashtun stories behind the proverbs, which are discussed below.

Examples:

قيامت به هله شي چي پښتون له ننگه پريوځي

*Doomsday will arrive when the Pakhtun says goodbye to his Nang (1203)
(Pg.130)*

This proverb highlights the importance of Nang, which is not a mere word but an important asset of Pashtunwali. This proverb conveys the idea that the end of the day will occur when Pashtun will forget the Nang. By Nang, they mean bravery, honor, courage, justice, respect for other's life and Self-pride. So, this value of Pashtunwali is similar to the digital value of individuality, which has clear and consistent rules like that of Nang in Pashtunwali. So, both values systems have a reliable system and stand for the right subject. Additionally, it demonstrates that digital platforms are unable to operate without transparent, reliable action, just like Pashtun society cannot work in the absence of Nang.

Additionally, in a proverb,

نه دومره خور شه چي خلک دې وخوري، نه دومره تريو شه چي خلک دې وکاندي

You should not be so sweet that you will be swallowed, nor be so bitter that you will be vomited.

This proverb demonstrates to keep the balance in life, and it is the command of Pashtunwali as well that Pashtun should be consistent, faithful, kind, and friendly, but not overly arrogant. He must keep the balance in the same manner in the digital world; trust is developed through reliable activity. So, both the values educate us that actual power comes from the balance of behavior.

Similarly, in the Pashto proverb and its context

پښتون چې پښتون نه لري زمکه دي پري پکه شي

When a Pashtun has no Pakhtu (Code of Honor), may he fills the hollows of the earth (Pg. 96)

This proverb reflects the importance of Pashtunwali, which is an ancient code of conduct present in every aspect of Pashtun life. Honor is the central tenet of Pashtunwali, and being honest and attached to the uniform principles of Pakhtu are necessary for Pashtun cultural identity. So, this cultural code influences the actions, the way of life, and the trust of the members of society. This concept shows a strong resemblance to the digital value of trust in which network, module, and digital channel are required to be trustworthy way with the user's needs and expectations. While Pakhtu or Pashtunwali teaches people to behave with honor, integrity, and accountability, predictability. In the digital world, it also develops customer trust and provides users with a reliable system to trust upon. So, in both Pashtun society and the digital world, trust is established through predictability and constancy. In Pashtun culture, a person is respected if he follows Pakhtu in the same way as the digital value of predictability is valued for its firmness, clarity, and reliability. So, in short, Pashtun, with no Pashtu, lost his dignity and honor just as the digital system lost its authenticity without predictability.

Service enabling is one of the values of digital systems, and it refers to the method of designing digital tools in such a way that they are easily accessible, helpful, and user-centric. The value of Service enabling of a digital system is similar to the Pashtun value of generosity and hospitality because both values focus on providing help and services to people. In Pashtun society, generosity and hospitality (Melmastya) are fundamental cultural values where guests are welcomed warmly with great respect, provided food and shelter without any expectation. They consider that guests are from the God side and it is their sacred duty to facilitate them. In the same way, service-enabling being a core value of the digital world aims to provide help to people to reach the information and services easily. Digital systems have designed devices, forums, and networks that provide free access to crucial services such as information, financial, health care, and educational material with the purpose of supporting needy people without any reason. So, both the values are coming from different backgrounds, service enabling from digital, generosity, and hospitality from Pashtun culture, but have the same purpose and work. Both aim to offer support, serve others, and show respect.

خدمت عظمت دی

Service is Greatness (924) (Rohi Mataluna, Pg. 238)

This proverb highlights the importance of service, generosity, and helping nature, which are not just the social norm but are a moral obligation rooted in the value system of Pashtunwali. This proverb is deeply connected to Pashtun society, where the notion of "Khydmat" (Service) is not seen as a sacred duty. The same value is appreciated by many poets, philosopher just like Aristotle says that "the best virtues are those that serves other well" while Leo Tolstoy asserted that "The whole purpose of life is to serve humanity". This notion of service is also a guidance

source for many significant movements such as Khudaie Khydmatgar (*Servant of God*) (1930-47) initiated by Khan Abdul Ghafar Khan. So, this Pashtun value of service has a close resemblance to the digital value of service enabling in today's world. Much like a Pashtun opens his gate to unknown travelers. Digital systems provide access, help, and opportunities to the people throughout the world. Digital systems are now helping people by offering online education, health care services, and a financial earning app with the same purpose of helping with respect and care. Just like Pashtuns never leave a guest without food, digital services also never let the user go unnoticed and unanswered. Therefore, the Pashtun value of Khydmat (Service) does not exist only in Pashtun culture, but it is also present in the digital network system.

The digital value of privacy is similar to the Pashtun value of Purdah, Ghairat, Honor, and family privacy, as both values emphasize the privacy and protection of the individual and the family as a whole. In a digital space, privacy is seen as a universal right where illegal access to user details, pictures, and discussions is perceived as a critical intrusion. In the same way, the Pashtun traditional values of Purdah, Ghairat, Honor, and Family privacy focus on protecting personal and domestic boundaries from the revealing of privacy. '*Purdah*' not only indicates veiling, but it is also the symbol of protecting women's honor and chastity. The idea of Ghairat shows mutual duty to protect the privacy and honor of a person, just like digital security. So, both the values emphasize the control of individual over their personal information and not to reveal the privacy of others. On the other hand, this system of privacy in the digital age is facing a greater risk. When someone's personal information is hacked and spread everywhere without any permission, it directly exploits the individual and their family's honor. Even a small act of exposure can ruin one's honor and lead to mental distress. The same is the case in Pashtun society. They are very conscious about their reputations, honor, and any sort of intrusion into their home privacy results in disgrace and hostility. Therefore, the Pashtun always try to keep their women in Purdah inside the home, and also safeguard their houses from being robbed because it is considered a shame in their Pashtun culture. In short, both Pashtun and Digital Value have faced some challenges, the digital in the form of hacking, and Pashtun Value in the form of robbing, abducting, disgrace, and unveiling.

In Pashtun culture, family privacy is kept very high, as in the following proverb:

اخڼلي در بخڼلي خو چي اوچ مي لمدۀ نه کړي

Keep the dough; leave me the dry flour. (83) (Rohi Mataluna, Pg. 24)

This proverb reflects an event where personal privacy is disturbed without the permission of the owner. A woman came to her fellow resident's house without consent and started kneading dough for herself. The householder is disturbed by the interference, but she understands that she cannot reverse what she has done earlier. So, she said to the woman that you may hold the dough, but do not drench my dry flour. It means she is requesting to avoid future intrusion. This idea is similar to the digital value of threat to privacy, where if someone's personal data, photo, or videos have been leaked out without his or her consent, that person

might not be able to reverse the mistake. However, he can request to people to stop further sharing it so that to protect the remaining honor and dignity. So, in short, both the Pashtun and digital value emphasize that if some mistake has happened unknowingly, you should stop it from further circulation because honor and dignity are not only in the act of avoiding mistakes but also in the step of preventing it from further exposure.

Similarly, in a proverb:

آدم خان دی پہ خیال گوروان راغله دے

“Mistake not Adam Khan for Shepherd” (6) Rohi Mataluna, (Pg 3)

This proverb highlights the incident of misinterpreting a person’s true value or character. It refers to a story of Adam Khan who disguised himself to meet Durkhani, his beloved, but he was caught and faced so many difficulties. A similar misunderstanding also occurs in the digital world when someone’s personal data is leaked online. So that person becomes sensitive to misjudgment, ridicule, and humiliation. It was not because of their real self but because of the other people disguise like someone known, and thus leak the data. So, the deterioration of online privacy can damage the honor just like the entry of a disguised man, Adam Khan, spoiling the Ghairat, Purdah, Izzat, and honor of the Durkhani family. Much like Adam Khan dressed in disguise to fulfill his mission in a secure way, people also apply privacy settings to protect their privacy and honor in this fast, judgmental world. So, in short, both Pashtun and digital systems emphasize that real and true dignity is rooted inside a person, but people are often mistaken by their apparent surface.

Similarly, in Pashtun culture, trust and loyalty have great value, but this trust is now at risk, and it is clearly shown in the following proverb;

ازمیبنت اول کال او تلین وو، اوس دم پہ دم دی

“A tested man was once reliable for a year, now he must prove himself daily” (115) (Rohi Mataluna, Pg. 34)

This proverb reflects the transformation in the traditional value where the trust and loyalty once achieved were not easily broken or forgotten, but now in today’s world, it needs regular validation. It indicates a world where trust and loyalty are exceptional, and even the most virtuous person should have to justify their value. The same change denotes the digital world as well, where privacy is no more secure and trust is lasting for a short time, such as Pashtuns strictly protecting their Ghairat, Izzat, and Purdah. The digital consumer needs to secure their personal information, pictures, and videos carefully. Only a small mistake, a wrong message, or a breached account can permanently destroy your dignity. So, both the Pashtun and digital world emphasize that trust, honor, and dignity should not be taken for granted, but must be protected all the time. So, in short, in both the digital and tribal setting, the real issue is that of trust, reputation, and privacy.

Pashtun people strictly follow this principle of safeguarding one's own honor and privacy, and do not blame others for mistakes, as in this proverb.

چي خداي کوي هنه به اوشي، خود وښن کوده تښکته وتره

Whatever God wills will happen, but it is better to bind tightly the forelegs of the camel. (650) (Rohi Mataluna, Pg 174)

This proverb teaches a lesson that, along with a firm belief in God, one should also hold individual responsibility. It means that faith in God does not indicate that you are free; instead, you have to do your job and let the result be on God. The story behind this proverb is that one person is telling the camel owner that what God decided will happen, but you should tie your camel tightly so that it can be protected from being stolen. In Pashtun tradition, Honor, Purdah, and Ghairat are highly respected, and Pashtun people make significant efforts to protect these values from any humiliation. Now in the digital world, these values can be damaged by the exposure of pictures, Videos, or any other information, just like the Pashtun emphasize on keeping the house door closed and the leg of the camel tied. The digital system also foretells applying strict privacy settings, remaining cautious, and being careful before sharing anything because securing 'honor' (Izzat) at the present time also means securing data

Durability is a digital value that indicates how long digital resources, such as content, programs, and software, stay reachable, functional, and protected without any loss of data. This digital value is similar to the Pashtun value of Honor, Nang, and respect for elders, as both of them concentrated on protecting the important value for a long time, and also to keep the respect of digital tools alive. In digital space, Durability refers to the capability of a machine to develop a network, platform, principles that remain stable for a long time and continue to help people for a long period. This value focuses on establishing trust and the duty of digital tools among people that have a long-term effect. In a similar manner, the Pashtun society also has a long-lasting system of honor, Ghairat, loyalty, and dignity, and they are protecting and passing these values from one generation to another.

Additionally, respect for elder is also an important value of Pashtun society that helps to maintain their culture strong and alive. They show respect for their advice, guidance, and wisdom. So, in short, both the value of the digital world, "durability," and the Pashtun society's "honor, elder respect" focus on securing something that is valuable so that it should not be forgotten, dishonored, and misused. Both values try to keep the virtual and Pashtun cultural trust so that it should stay strong for the next generation.

Pashtun people have a high level of respect for their elders, and they take their advice in difficult situations such as in the proverb.

له شگورسي نه جوريري

A Rope cannot be made from soil. (The Pashto Proverbs, Pg. 119)

This proverb reveals a complex situation that cannot be handled without an elder person. Pashtuns have a great respect for elderly people; they consider them a source of wisdom, advice, and learning for the new generation. The story behind this proverb is that a King ordered to kill every white beard man because they were of no use, so everyone followed the order except one person. He secretly protected his own father. Time passes, the King again orders to make a rope from soil, but no one has the ability to make it. Once, one person said to King that I will make the rope, but first you should make a model of it for me so that I may proceed. By hearing this, the King gets surprised and asks the person It is not your idea, tell me the truth and that person tells him that at the time of your first order, I saved my father. So, the King feels sorry for what he has done earlier, and now he realizes that old people are not worthless; they also have a significant role in society. So, from that day, he stopped killing older people. It indicates that the elderly people must be protected like the reliable data of a digital system. In digital world, 'mentoring' refers to the process of guiding and training of young user. Much like the old man upholds ancient knowledge to resolve the challenge, a reliable network also help in protecting young user to have safe digital experiences. In short, both the Pashtun and Digital value give an important message of preserving those people and data that convey a prolonged standard and intelligence.

Similarly, in Pashtun tradition, the respect of elder people is not merely for the reason of politeness and respect, but also because of their guidance, intelligence, and strength, such as in the proverb;

مال دې لار شي، سر دې لار شي، پت دې نه ځي

A man may lose his wealth and his head but not his honor. (1266) (Rohi Mataluna, Pg. 327)

This proverb demonstrates that if a person loses his money, his life, his everything, he should not lose his honor because it describes the individual's real and inherent value. That is why this proverb emphasizes that honor should be protected at any cost or price. In today's virtual world, the same rules are implemented for Durability that virtual resources or data should stay protected, invariant, and should be used for a long time despite environmental variation and system breakdown. Much like the Pashtun resist to sacrifice their honor, the digital network also protected their essential information and data from distortion. So, Pashtun people give preference to honor over wealth, just like the digital system prioritizes stability, reliability, and consistency of information in the digital world. So, in short, both emphasize the value of staying strong, unchanging, and being reliable.

Similarly, in Pashtun society, 'honor' and 'shame' are strongly connected to the identity of a person, especially with the behavior of women that how they express themselves in the community. Such as in the following proverb;

Conclusion

The present study reveals some of the major threats and problems that the persona encountered, including the loss of their personal information, videos, and chats, as well as a lack of parental attention in the digital world. All these threats left various mental scars on the persona, including stress, anxiety, disturbance, disappointment, and isolation from the rest of the world. Apart from psychological issues, the participants also loss their honor and reputation in society because of the online exposure. This study adopted a hybrid model, persona, diagnostic map, and Affinity diagramming as a theoretical framework. The persona and diagnostic map are used to identify the hope, problems, causes, and impacts of bad digital experiences on the personas. Affinity diagramming was used to collect data from interviews, surveys, and various research articles to identify Pashtun cultural values. The whole study revolves around three core paradigms of Pashtun Values, Digital values, and their interactions in the digital world. After collecting all the values of Pashtun and digital world, the researchers compare them with each other and found that some values of Pashtunwali have parallels in the digital world as well such as, Pashtunwali, nang, honor, purdah, mashari exhibits in the digital values of trustworthiness, service enabling, confidentiality, protection against hacking, and privacy. After collecting all these values, the researchers then analyze the Pashtun stories behind the Pashto proverbs, with a special focus on finding the aforementioned values within them. The researchers concludes that by recognizing cultural values and then using technological tools to protect and promote them can help to create a link between the traditional and digital world. Thus, the digitization of cultural values will not only preserve them but also make them meaningfully accessible in the digital world. Furthermore, the researchers maintain that a lack of value-based education is root cause of bad digital experiences. In conclusion, the present study emphasizes that the digitization of Pashtun stories behind proverbs, which contain traditional values, plays an important role in improving digital experiences.

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